

ERSKINE CALDWELL – POWERFUL AND EVOCATIVE PROSE OWNER

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Annotation. The discussion below is about the prose of Erskine Caldwell, an early 20th-century writer whose works are notable for their raw, unflinching portrayal of rural Southern life.

Key words. Prose, writer, novel, short story, nonfiction collection, autobiography.

Erskine Preston Caldwell is an American prose writer, a representative of the realist trend in literature. Born into the family of a Presbyterian minister, he spent his childhood in the remote towns of the South, similar to those where the young hero of his autobiographical story "Georgia Boy" (1943) lived. Leaving home at the age of 17, Caldwell changed many professions: a farm laborer, a cotton gin worker, a bricklayer, and a reporter for local newspapers and studied at the university for about three years. He began to write in 1928. Early stories were included in the first collection - "American Earth" (1931). In 1930, two stories appeared: "The Bastard" and "Poor Fool".

Widespread fame brought him novels "Tobacco Road" (1932), soon staged on Broadway, and "God's Little Acre" (1933). These novels are united by the theme of the dramatic fate of the white sharecroppers of the South.

In 1937, Caldwell, together with the artist-photographer Margaret Bourke-White, published the photo album *You Have Seen Their Faces*¹. In 1939 they get married - this marriage lasted until 1942. For a long time, Caldwell maintained close ties with the USSR. His works have been repeatedly translated into Russian since 1938. From June to September 1941, the writer was a correspondent in Moscow. As a result, he published nonfiction books "*Moscow Under Fire*" and "*All-Out on the Road to Smolensk*" (1942), as well as the novel "*All Night Long*", (1942) - about the partisan movement in the

¹ *You Have Seen Their Faces* (Brown Thrasher Books Ser.) Paperback – February 1, 1995

USSR. Subsequently, the writer visited the USSR in 1959 and 1963.²

Caldwell's work is characterized by a heightened attention to ordinary people, the heroes of his books are most often people of physical labor. The skill of building a plot, the richness of the language palette, the amazing capacity of the word, the irony of intonations - all this is, as it were, covered up by external equanimity, good-natured mockery. The reader is ready to laugh at funny characters and situations, but, having thought about the meaning of what was told, he is convinced of the author's intransigence to evil, cruelty, and social inequality.

Caldwell wrote 25 novels, 150 short stories, twelve nonfiction collections, two autobiographies, and two books for young readers.³ He also edited the influential American Folkways series, a 28-volume series of books about different regions of the United States.⁴

Characteristics of short stories by Erskine Caldwell:

- **Regionalism:** Caldwell often set his stories in the American South and wrote about the lives of poor, rural people.
- **Social commentary:** Many of Caldwell's stories explore issues of poverty, racism, and class struggle.
- **Dark humor:** Caldwell often used humor to highlight the absurdity of his characters' situations.
- **Simple language:** Caldwell's writing style is straightforward and easy to understand, which makes his stories accessible to a wide audience.
- **Realistic characters:** Caldwell's characters are often flawed and complex, reflecting the realities of human nature.
- **Vivid descriptions:** Caldwell's stories are filled with vivid descriptions of the natural world, which often reflects the emotions and experiences of his characters.
- **Irony:** Many of Caldwell's stories contain ironic twists that reveal the contradictions and complexities of human behavior.
- **Symbolism:** Caldwell often uses symbolism to convey deeper meanings and themes in his stories.
- **Psychological depth:** Caldwell's stories often delve into the psychological motivations of his characters, revealing their innermost thoughts and desires.
- **Social criticism:** Caldwell's stories often criticize social institutions and norms, challenging readers to question their own assumptions and beliefs.⁵
- **Political corruption:** In *"My Old Man's Political Appointment,"* Caldwell explores the corrupt world of politics and the ways in which it can be used to exploit and manipulate people.

Erskine Caldwell's prose is characterized by its raw, unflinching portrayal of rural Southern life in the early 20th century.⁶ His writing is often marked by vivid descriptions of poverty,

²Erskine Caldwell, Margaret Bourke-White, and the Popular Front: Photojournalism in Russia By Jay E. Caldwell pages 15-21

³"Biography" (<https://web.archive.org/web/20110929144645/http://www.johnwade.com/biography.htm>). John Wade. Archived from the original (<http://www.johnwade.com/biography.htm>) on September 29, 2011 . Retrieved September 29, 2011.

⁴Firsts Magazine, v.8, n.5 (May 1988).

⁵Louis Palmer Bourgeois Blues: Class, Whiteness, and Southern Gothic in Early Faulkner and Caldwell [Vol. 22, No. 1/2, Special Issue: Faulkner and Whiteness \(Fall 2006/Spring 2007\)](#), pp. 120-139 (20 pages)

violence, and sexual tension. Caldwell's style is spare and direct, with a focus on the physical details of his characters' lives. He often uses regional dialect and vernacular to create a sense of authenticity and to capture the rhythms of Southern speech. Despite the often bleak subject matter of his work, Caldwell's writing is also marked by a sense of humor and a deep empathy for his characters. Overall, his prose is powerful and evocative, capturing the harsh realities of life in the American South with unvarnished honesty.

Caldwell died April 11, 1987 in Paradise Valley, Arizona.

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⁶[Eddison Monroe 6 Best Erskine Caldwell Books to Read – Great American Literature](#)